

Characterisation of new *in vitro* models and identification of potentially active drugs in angiosarcoma

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ABSTRACT

Angiosarcoma is a rare soft tissue sarcoma originating from endothelial cells. Given that current treatments for advanced disease have shown limited efficacy, alternative therapies need to be identified. In rare diseases, patient-derived cell models are crucial for screening anti-tumour activity. In this study, cell line models were characterised in 2D and 3D cultures. The cell lines' growth, migration and invasion capabilities were explored, confirming them as useful tools for preclinical angiosarcoma studies. By screening a drug library, we identified potentially effective compounds: 8-amino adenosine impacted cell growth and inhibited migration and invasion at considerably low concentrations as a single agent. No synergistic effect was detected when combining with paclitaxel, gemcitabine or doxorubicin. These results suggest that this compound could be a potentially useful drug in the treatment of AGS.

1. Introduction

Angiosarcoma (AGS) is a soft tissue sarcoma (STS) derived from malignant endothelial cells of vascular or lymphatic origin. This tumour accounts for 1%–2% of STS, commonly found as a scalp or face lesion [1, 2]. It typically exhibits aggressive behaviour, with a 5-year survival rate of approximately 31% and a median overall survival of 7 months for patients with metastatic disease. Wide Surgical resection is the main

treatment for resectable disease, whereas chemotherapy (based on taxanes or anthracyclines) is used to treat advanced disease [3].

Due to its low incidence, developing clinical studies focused on AGS is problematic. Therefore, patients with AGS are usually included in pooled STS clinical trials or in small studies, making the identification of effective therapies or specific associated biomarkers difficult.

AGS cells typically express vimentin due to their mesenchymal origins, and endothelial markers such as CD34, CD31 or D240 are

Abbreviations: 8AA, 8-amino adenosine; AGS, angiosarcoma; CTG, CellTiter-Glo; DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide; DSRT, Drug sensitivity and resistance testing; DSS, drug sensitivity score; IHC, immunohistochemistry; SB, sepantronium bromide; STS, soft tissue sarcoma; SRB, sulphorhodamine B; TCA, trichloroacetic acid.

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commonly used for the differential diagnosis. However, loss of these markers can be observed in the dedifferentiation process. ERG is another useful marker, and the absence of melanocytic markers (S100) can help distinguish AGS from melanoma [4]. Additionally, epithelioid AGS can express cytokeratins, leading to confusion with poorly differentiated carcinomas. Although activating *KIT* mutations has not been described, some series report *KIT* positivity in 50% of cases [5]. Abnormalities in *TP53* have also been reported, and *cMYC* expression has been related to radiation-associated AGS [6].

Developing *in vitro* models for rare tumours like AGS is crucial to improving our understanding of the disease and to test novel therapies. *In vitro* anticancer drug testing is essential for identifying effective therapies; however, only around 5% of the drugs with demonstrated efficacy in the preclinical setting correlate with efficacy in clinical trials [7]. These tests are typically performed on 2D cultures in which all cells are disposed in a monolayer and are equally exposed to the drug. *In vitro* studies in AGS are scarce and are mainly focused on the analysis of cell proliferation. 3D models better mimic the tumour architectural disposition and play a leading role in drug testing. To our knowledge, there have been no 3D cell culture studies in AGS cell lines.

This study aims to identify alternative effective therapies in AGS. We performed high-throughput compound screening (HTS) on 2 AGS cell lines cultured in 2D and 3D. Interestingly, several drugs demonstrated a growth inhibition in all tested models, and some demonstrated an impact on other cellular features, with 8AA as the most promising agent.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Cell culture and reagents

We cultured the human AGS cell lines ISO-HAS-1 and MO-LAS-B (Resource Centre for Biomedical Research, Institute of Development, Aging, and Cancer, Tohoku University, Japan) in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (Merck; Darmstadt, Germany) supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum. The cell lines were routinely tested to detect mycoplasma contamination with the MycoAlert kit (Lonza; Rockland, ME, USA) and were authenticated by short tandem repeat profiling performed by the Genomics Core Facility at the Biomedical Research Institute Alberto Sols CSIC-UAM (Madrid) with the GenePrint 10 System (Promega; Madison, WI, USA), following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.2. Immunohistochemistry

Cell pellets were collected and fixed in 70% ethanol before paraffin embedding. Haematoxylin and eosin staining was used for cell examination and localisation.

We performed immunohistochemistry (IHC) for the markers described below. Four- μ m sections were cut with a semiautomatic microtome HM3508 (MICROM), deparaffinised and rehydrated in water. Antigen retrieval was performed in a DAKO PT Link (Agilent; Santa Clara, CA, USA). Peroxidase activity was blocked with Dako Protein block for 10 min, then incubated for 1 h with primary antibodies (VIM #IR630, CD34 #IR632, D240 #IR055, ERG #IR65961, panCK #IR053, CD117 #A4502, *cMYC* #257261 and p53 #IR616). An Envision kit (Agilent) was used for visualisation, and the slides were counterstained with haematoxylin.

Images were acquired under bright field microscopy with an Olympus BX51 microscope coupled to an Olympus DP70 camera (Olympus; Tokyo, Japan) at 40x with Image-Pro Plus software (version 6.0) (Media Cybernetics; Rockville, MD, USA).

2.3. Cell proliferation assay

Cells were seeded in 96-well plates for 2D and 3D experiments (#3596 and #7007; Corning, NY, USA), incubated for 72 h for 2D and 14

days for 3D, at 37 °C in 5% CO₂. The 2D cells were fixed with trichloroacetic acid (TCA, Merck) and stained with sulphorhodamine B (SRB, Merck) as previously described [8]. Absorbance was measured at 564 nm employing a GloMax microplate reader (Promega). For 3D, sphere diameter was monitored with Celigo (Nexcelom; Lawrence, MA, USA).

2.4. Drug screening

Drug sensitivity and resistance testing (DSRT) was performed with a 527-compound library plated at 5 concentrations for each drug, which covers a 10,000-fold concentration range (Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM), High-Throughput Biomedicine Unit at the University of Helsinki, Finland) [9]. The lyophilised pre-plated compounds were dissolved in culture medium immediately before their use and transferred to 384-well plates containing cells for the 2D and 3D experiments (#3764 and #ULA-384 U-020, Corning).

Briefly, cells were seeded one day before for the 2D experiments, and 4 days before for the 3D experiments. The cells were incubated with the compounds for 72 h, and viability was measured with a CellTiter-Glo (CTG) assay (Promega), employing a GloMax (Promega) plate reader and the Celigo Platform (Nexcelom). The data were normalised to negative and positive control wells containing dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and 100- μ M benzethonium chloride, respectively [10].

To assess quantitative drug profiles for each sample, we calculated a drug sensitivity score (DSS) based on the measured dose-response curves using Breeze DSRT analysis platform (<https://breeze.fimm.fi/>) [11]. DSS is an integrative and robust drug response metric based on the normalised area under the curve, which considers all 4 curve-fitting parameters in the logistic model.

2.5. IC₅₀ determination

To determine the specific drug effects, cells were seeded in 96-well plates and exposed to increasing concentrations of the selected drugs for 72 h at 37 °C in 5% CO₂. The concentration ranges used were established based on the screening experiments. The SRB assay was used for 2D cultures, and IC₅₀ values were calculated based on absorbance values measured using a microplate reader (BioRad; Hercules, CA, USA). IC₅₀ for 3D cultures was determined with a CTG assay (Promega) as previously described. In both cases, IC₅₀ values were calculated by nonlinear regression analysis by GraphPad Prism software (San Diego, CA, USA). Cells were previously exposed to DMSO (0.1%) and compared to controls with growth medium to establish that there were no differences in growth.

2.6. Cell cytotoxicity

Cells were seeded 1 day before for the 2D experiments, and 4 days before for the 3D experiments. The cells were incubated with the compounds for 72 h, and cytotoxicity was explored with a CellTox Green assay (Promega) employing the Celigo image cytometer (Nexcelom).

2.7. Cell cycle analysis

Cells were treated for 24 h with selected compounds. After fixation in 85% ethanol and incubation with propidium iodide solution (Invitrogen; Waltham, MA, USA), the cell cycle was analysed with Celigo (Nexcelom).

2.8. Migration and invasion

The invasion and migration capabilities were evaluated in 2D and 3D conditions. For the monolayer culture experiments, cells were treated with the selected drugs for 72 h and then transferred into 8- μ m-pore Transwell inserts in low serum (1%) conditions (#354578, Corning).

Matrigel pre-coated inserts (#354480, Corning) were used for the invasion experiments. After 24 h, the top chamber cells were removed using a cotton swab, and the inserts were fixed by the Diff-Quick method (QCA; Tarragona, Spain). Photographs of the inserts were taken with an Olympus microscope at 40x magnification. In the 3D conditions, cells were plated and spheroids were allowed to form and grow for 4 days. Then, the drug was added at the corresponding IC_{50} dose and incubated for 3 additional days. Subsequently, the spheroids were transferred onto a Matrigel layer for migration assays or were embedded for invasion assays. The spheroids were monitored for 3 days and images were acquired with Celigo.

2.9. Drug combinations

Pair-wise drug combinations were explored. Treatment was established for 72 h, with the concentration range based on each single-drug experiment. According to a 6×6 dose-response matrix design, the effect of the single drugs, as well as the drug combinations, were tested. Experiments were analysed employing the Synergy-Finder R package, as previously described [12,13].

2.10. Statistical analysis

Experiments were performed at least twice. The results are shown as the mean \pm SD. Statistical analyses were performed with GraphPad Prism 7. The significance of differences between 2 groups was assessed with Student's unpaired 2-tailed t-tests. Differences were considered significant when the obtained p-values were less than 0.05.

3. Results

3.1. Cell line characterisation

Representative bright field images of the 2D and 3D cultures as well as the proliferation plots can be observed in Fig. 1. Both cell lines presented a spindle-like morphology in 2D and compact spheroids in 3D. Regarding proliferation, the MO-LAS-B cells grew faster in 2D than the ISO-HAS-1 cells, whereas in 3D the MO-LAS-B spheroids compacted their structure over time and the ISO-HAS-1 maintained a similar size. Both cell lines showed migration and invasion capabilities in 2D; in 3D, however, migration was only observed in MO-LAS-B.

Haematoxylin and eosin stain and IHC for some markers were

performed on the cellular pellets. Both cell lines showed positive vimentin expression and negative cytokeratin expression. MO-LAS-B was strongly positive for CD34, whereas ISO-HAS-1 was not; however, both cell lines showed a diffuse staining of D240 and ERG, supporting their vascular origin. Additionally, both were negative for cKIT and cMYC, and p53 was highly positive in ISO-HAS-1 and negative in MO-LAS-B (Additional supplementary file 1).

3.2. Drug screening and candidate selection

The assay was run using 2 AGS cell lines cultured in 2D and 3D conditions. We employed 384-well plates for screening. After 72 h of compound exposure, and based on CTG values, DSS scores were calculated. The compound screening revealed variations across the 2 cell lines and between bi- and tridimensional cultures. Candidate drugs were selected when DSS was >10 in 2D and 3D, for both cell lines. This threshold was passed by 12 compounds (Fig. 2).

Interestingly, most of them have been implicated in apoptosis promotion and cell cycle inhibition. Two drugs are immunomodulators, and one inhibits transcription. Another 2 are epigenetic modifiers.

3.3. Hit compounds validation

The top 5 DSS compounds were determined to be effective candidates: abexinostat, 8-amino-adenosine (8AA), romidepsin, sepantronium bromide (SB) and alvocidib.

Abexinostat showed the highest mean DSS value; however, it also demonstrated a high deviation between 2D and 3D approaches, and the compound was not available when the study began. Ultimately, 8AA, romidepsin, sepantronium bromide and alvocidib were selected for further validation. The toxicity profile of the drugs was also explored in healthy control bone marrow cells, to evaluate the differential response between cancer and healthy cells, and we calculated the selective DSS value for each drug. 8AA showed the highest selective DSS value, indicating the most effective cancer cell-specific response among the tested drugs.

We performed a comprehensive 96-well plate dose-response assay to validate the obtained results with the 4 selected compounds. Proliferation was measured by SRB and CTG assays in 2D and 3D, respectively, after 72 h of drug exposure. The 4 drugs were highly effective as a single agent in both AGS models, demonstrating a decrease in cell proliferation with increasing drug concentrations. Representative drug response

Fig. 1. Morphology and proliferative characteristics of the cell lines studied. a) Photographs in 2D (upper) and 3D (lower panel) cultures. Scale bar represents 500 μ m; b) Quantification of the proliferative capacity in 2D (upper) and 3D (lower panel) cultures.

Fig. 2. Top Hit selected compounds. a) Absolute selective drug sensitivity score (DSS) values for both cell lines and 2D and 3D culture. Yellow areas indicate low values, darkening to orange as the values increase indicate high values respectively b) Overall average DSS of compounds exhibiting the highest values. 8AA: 8-amino-adenosine; SB: sepantronium bromide.

graphs for each cell line and culture condition are included in [additional supplementary file 2](#).

The summary of IC_{50} values is shown in [Table 1](#). The 8AA and sepantronium bromide were effective in micrometre concentrations, whereas romidepsin and alvocidib were effective in a nM range. All compounds showed an increase in their 3D IC_{50} values compared with the monolayer culture, except 8AA for ISO-HAS-1. In 2D, all drugs were more effective in MO-LAS-B; in the 3D setting, however, the differences in the 4 tested compounds were not defined by this pattern. Romidepsin and sepantronium bromide were more active in MO-LAS-B, and 8AA and alvocidib in ISO-HAS-1. Major differences in the IC_{50} values were observed with sepantronium bromide in 2D, and with this drug and romidepsin in 3D.

Additionally, IC_{50} values for drugs routinely used in sarcoma treatment were established. Gemcitabine and paclitaxel were effective in the nM range, whereas this was true for doxorubicin at μ M concentrations; all 3 compounds demonstrated an increase in their 3D IC_{50} values (except paclitaxel in ISO-HAS-1). As observed for the candidate drugs, ISO-HAS-1 was less sensitive than MO-LAS-B for these 3 classical chemotherapies in 2D. The tendency was less pronounced in the 3D experiments, and even reverted for paclitaxel.

3.4. Cell cycle and cytotoxicity

We examined the cell cycle and cytotoxicity ([Fig. 3](#) and [additional supplementary file 3](#)). No substantial modifications in cell cycle were observed when the cells were treated with 8AA or alvocidib. Romidepsin produced a significant decrease in G0/G1 and an increase in G2/M phase cells in both cell lines. Sepantronium bromide promoted a significant increase in the S phase and a decrease in the G2/M phases, but only in

Table 1

IC_{50} values for selected compounds and other used drugs.

Cell line	ISO-HAS-1		MO-LAS-B	
	IC_{50} 2D	IC_{50} 3D	IC_{50} 2D	IC_{50} 3D
8AA (μM)	0.65 \pm 0.05	0.28 \pm 0.15	0.42 \pm 0.07	1.10 \pm 0.15
Romidepsin (nM)	3.19 \pm 0.94	82.43 \pm 15.06	1.23 \pm 0.15	2.05 \pm 0.49
SB (μM)	5.65 \pm 1.87	31.09 \pm 17.35	0.10 \pm 0.04	3.46 \pm 1.12
Alvocidib (nM)	170.83 \pm 23.48	187.70 \pm 51.36	130.00 \pm 10.51	249.36 \pm 38.52
Doxorubicin (μM)	0.63 \pm 0.02	0.97 \pm 0.01	0.10 \pm 0.05	1.45 \pm 0.38
Gemcitabine (nM)	3522.00 \pm 521.80	628,425.00 \pm 126017.00	7.80 \pm 1.60	614,033.30 \pm 177065.50
Paclitaxel (nM)	10,940.00 \pm 235.20	10,733.70 \pm 2561.40	1.90 \pm 1.20	40,570.00 \pm 2251.00

8AA: 8-amino-adenosine; SB: sepantronium bromide.

ISO-HAS-1 ([Fig. 3a](#)). All tested compounds showed a cytotoxic effect to a different extent in both cell lines, and in 2D and 3D conditions ([Fig. 3b](#)).

3.5. Migration and invasion

Migration and invasion capabilities were not modified by romidepsin, alvocidib or sepantronium bromide. However, treatment with 8AA significantly reduced both cell migration and invasion compared with untreated control cells ([Fig. 4](#)).

Under 3D conditions, when MO-LAS-B spheroids were exposed to 8AA, a substantial reduction of the migration front was observed at 72 h compared with the untreated control ([Fig. 5](#)).

3.6. Drug combinations

To further investigate the potential of 8AA, its combination with doxorubicin, gemcitabine and paclitaxel was explored, chemotherapeutic agents that are frequently used in patients with advanced AGS. A 6 \times 6 dose-response matrix was designed with 8AA and these 3 drugs. None of the explored combinations showed a synergistic effect in either of the cell lines. Representative experimental data are shown in [additional supplementary file 4](#).

4. Discussion

AGS is a rare and aggressive type of STS that is associated with a poor prognosis in the metastatic setting. Although some patients can respond to classic drugs (such as doxorubicin, paclitaxel or gemcitabine), progression-free survival and overall survival are poor [14,15]. Given that the addition of antiangiogenic agents to chemotherapy has not demonstrated an improvement in clinical activity, its use is not recommended [16]. Therefore, metastatic AGS is an unmet medical need, and the need to identify active therapies is urgent.

The rarity and heterogeneity of STS makes the development of clinical trials by specific subtypes, such as AGS, difficult; thus, the identification of novel therapies is a major challenge. In this scenario, cellular models are a promising tool for pharmacological screening.

The 2 established cell lines selected for this study were ISO-HAS-1 and MO-LAS-B, both of which have been used in previous studies. Some drugs have been tested and proven to be effective, such as rapamycin and celecoxib for ISO-HAS-1 and olaparib for MO-LAS-B. The few available *in vitro* studies have focused mainly on the analysis of cell growth and the effect on invasiveness. Although other drugs have been shown to have potential *in vitro* activity in human AGS, these therapeutic options have not been developed [17–19].

In the present study, 527 compounds were screened in both AGS cell lines, in 2D and 3D cultures. Four candidate compounds (8AA, romidepsin, sepantronium bromide and alvocidib) were selected for further

Fig. 3. Effect on cell cycle and cytotoxic damage produced by the selected drugs. a) Plots by cell cycle phase from a representative experiment; b) Average percentage distribution of cell cycle phases from 2 independent experiments; c) Micrographs from Celltox staining in 2D (top) and 3D (bottom panels). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.0001$. 8AA: 8-amino-adenosine; SB: sepantronium bromide.

validation based on the DSS values, all of which showed anti-proliferative and cytotoxic effects at various levels in both cell lines. The toxicity of these selected drugs in normal bone marrow cells was also explored, revealing that 8AA was less toxic than the other compounds, in line with previous reports using this drug [20].

8AA has been previously explored in cellular models of multiple myeloma, mantle cell lymphoma and breast cancer, showing activity affecting cell proliferation [20–22]. This compound has been previously linked to metabolic dysfunction. 8AA triggers ATP level decrease and

mRNA synthesis inhibition, which impacts on multiple pathways, including survival programs and apoptosis [23]. Romidepsin is a histone deacetylase inhibitor, and alvocidib is a nonspecific cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor. Both compounds have shown some effectiveness in cutaneous T-cell lymphoma. Sepantronium bromide blocks survivin expression, and other mechanisms of action, such as DNA damage, have also been proposed [24]. A previous study observed the antiproliferative capacity of sepantronium bromide in the AGS cell line ISO-HAS-B (derived from the same patient as ISO-HAS-1) [25,26].

Fig. 4. 8AA inhibits migration and invasion of AGS cells in 2D. Left panels include inserts bright field micrographs, the scale bar representing 500 μ m. Right panels show the quantification of data as mean \pm SD for a) ISO-HAS-1 and b) MO-LAS-B. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.0001; 8AA: 8-amino-adenosine; SB: sepantronium bromide.

Fig. 5. 8AA inhibits invasion of MO-LAS-B cells in 3D. a) Representative bright field images. Red underline the migration front and scale bar represents 500 μ m; b) Quantification data plot shown as the mean \pm SD for control and treated cells.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to show the antitumoural activity of 8AA, romidepsin and alvocidib in AGS cell lines, and the first study considering these 3 drugs and sepantronium bromide in 2D and 3D conditions, exploring not only proliferation, but also cell cycle, migration and invasion properties.

Regarding the cell cycle, the most significant results, which were consistent in both cell lines, were observed with romidepsin exposure. Some previous studies had reported that romidepsin promotes G2/M arrest in urothelial carcinoma, in line with our results. We also observed a decreased G0/G1 cell number, in opposition to a phase arrest reported in lung, colon and endometrial cancer cell lines [27–29]. Sepantronium bromide and alvocidib have also shown cell cycle arrest with various cell line models [30,31]. We did not observe a significant impact on AGS cell lines treated with sepantronium bromide, alvocidib or 8AA. This result could indicate that the effect on the cell cycle could be cell line dependent; however, further studies need to be performed to confirm these results.

Infiltrative growth is another important characteristic for evaluation of cell model aggressiveness. Importantly, in the case of alvocidib, a reduction in migration and metastatic capacity has been observed in

some tumour cell lines, including osteosarcoma [31]. In our study, a significant reduction in invasiveness was only observed in the ISO-HAS-1 cell line; thus, further study would be necessary to explain this difference. Romidepsin and other histone deacetylase inhibitors have been shown to inhibit migration and/or invasion capacities in breast, ovarian and renal carcinoma cell lines [32–34]. However, no reduction of invasion and migration capabilities was observed in the AGS cell lines. Sepantronium bromide has been shown to have an antimigration effect on oral squamous cell carcinoma and osteosarcoma cell lines [35,36]. In our study, only ISO-HAS-1 showed a significant reduction in invasiveness. There are limited studies in other cell lines on the effects of 8AA [37]. Drug treatment consistently reduced 2D migration and invasion ability in both lines. This reduction was further validated in MO-LAS-B, which has 3D migration capacity.

Based on the antitumoural properties and the toxicity profile in bone marrow, the most promising drug identified in our study was 8AA, which produced a decrease in cell proliferation, cell viability, invasiveness and migration in both cell lines.

We additionally explored the effect of 3 commonly used drugs in AGS: doxorubicin, paclitaxel and gemcitabine. Antiproliferative effect

differences were observed in both cell lines, with MO-LAS-B being more sensitive to the 3 drugs. We explored their combination with 8AA to obtain a more active treatment, without success. The effect of the drug combination resembled that of 8AA alone, suggesting that 8AA could be useful in AGS as monotherapy. Interestingly, this effect was demonstrated in both cell lines, which have different sensitivities to classical drugs, including taxanes.

The results suggest that 8AA has a potent antitumour activity against AGS in cellular 2D and 3D models, inhibiting proliferation, but also with an impact on migration and invasion. Further studies incorporating *in vivo* validation are recommended to strengthen the evidence for the compound anti-tumour activity and its potential role in clinical application.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Victoria Heredia-Soto: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Francisco Escudero:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jose Pozo-Kreilinger:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Maria Miguel:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Silvia Rodriguez-Marrero:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Swapnil Potdar:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **marta mendiola:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Andres Redondo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jaime Feliu:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Eduardo Ortiz-Cruz:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Alberto Berjon:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jani Saarela:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marta Mendiola reports financial support was provided by VYDA-GEIS. Andres Redondo reports financial support was provided by VYDA-GEIS. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with MSD that includes: consulting or advisory. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP that includes: consulting or advisory. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with GSK that includes: consulting or advisory. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with Eisai Inc that includes: funding grants. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with PharmaMar Ltd that includes: funding grants. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP that includes: consulting or advisory. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with GSK that includes: travel reimbursement. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with PharmaMar Ltd that includes: travel reimbursement. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with Roche that includes: travel reimbursement. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with Pfizer that includes: travel reimbursement. Marta Mendiola reports a relationship with Biocartis that includes: travel reimbursement. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with MSD that includes: consulting or advisory. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP that includes: consulting or advisory. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with GSK that includes: consulting or advisory. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with Eisai Inc that includes: consulting or advisory. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with Clovis Oncology that includes: consulting or advisory. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with PharmaMar Ltd that includes: consulting or advisory. Andres Redondo reports a relationship with Boehringer Ingelheim

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2024.116397](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2024.116397).

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